

README

All files are gathered in `dataset_and_scripts.zip`.

All scripts are written for python 3.7.7. Required python packages are:

- `numpy` (1.21.6), `pandas` (1.3.5), `matplotlib` (3.5.1), `scipy` (1.7.3), `json5` (0.9.5), `qtt` (1.2.4), `openpyxl` (3.0.7), `uncertainties` (3.1.6)
- `core_tools` version 1.4.26 (https://github.com/stephanlphilips/core_tools)

Figures can be created by opening `planar_2D_QD_array_figures.py` (e.g. in Spyder) and executing it cell by cell. To reproduce the analysis of the lever arms and electron temperature estimates please execute `ana_script_lever_arm_and_electron_temperature_via_SET_with_err.py` cell by cell.

Raw data is located in the folder `raw_data`, descriptions and additional parameters belonging to the raw data can be found in `data_overview_sheets`.